

**Co-creation Practice in the Development of Non-pharmacological
Interventions for People with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary
Disease: A Health CASCADE Scoping Review Protocol**

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Abstract

Objective

The overall aim of this scoping review is to describe the co-creation practice used when developing Non-pharmacological Interventions (NPI) for people with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD). Specifically, the review will address the core constructs, methods used, and challenges faced in the co-creation practice in order to aid planning and commissioning of future research.

Introduction

There is well-documented scientific evidence to prove that NPIs can improve quality of life, slow down deterioration, relieve symptoms, and improve health for people with COPD. In addition to the improvement of patients' health outcomes, NPIs also reduce health care utilization and the cost burdens associated with COPD. When compared to traditional expert-driven approaches, applying a co-creation process may result in more useable, acceptable, and effective NPIs. However, there is a lack of evidence-informed guidance to incorporate co-creation practice into the development of NPIs for COPD. The literature on reporting co-creation practice in the development of NPIs for COPD deserves close scrutiny to inform future co-creation practice, policy and research in order to improve the quality of care.

Inclusion Criteria

Studies describing utilizing or/and evaluating co-creation practice in the development of NPIs for people with COPD will be included.

Methods

This review will follow the methodology proposed by Arksey and O'Malley for scoping reviews and report by PRISMA-ScR framework. The search will include PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and Web of Science Core Collection (all editions). Studies will be selected according to a three-step process, including i) managing search results and removing duplicates, ii) title and abstract screening, and iii) full-text screening. Extracted data will be displayed in diagrammatic or tabular format. A narrative summary will accompany the tabulated and/or charted results, describing how the results relate to the review objective and research questions, as well as how the results may inform future co-creation practice in developing NPIs for people with COPD.

Keywords: co-creation, non-pharmacological intervention, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

1. Introduction

1.1 Burden of COPD

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is one of the world's leading non-communicable causes of death.¹ Nearly 10% of the global population above the age of 40 years is affected by COPD.² It is a common, preventable, and treatable disease that is characterized with abnormalities of the airways which are predominantly caused by exposure to noxious gases and particulates over a long period of time.¹ COPD are regarded a priority for action in the health sector, not only because of the severe body impact, but also because the social and economic consequences that greatly impact on people's quality of life.^{3,4} As a progressive life-threatening lung disease that causes breathlessness,⁵ COPD has a detrimental impact on patients' physical health, mental health and social well-being.⁶⁻⁸ Exacerbations, defined as an increase in the severity of a disease or its signs and symptoms⁹, are common in people with COPD, and can lead to worsened disease, comorbidity, hospitalizations and even death.¹⁰ Exacerbations resulting in hospitalization increase treatment expenses and place a tremendous care burden on patients, their families, and the healthcare system.^{6,11} Despite the fact that the definition of COPD is the presence of chronic airflow limitation, COPD is perceived as "a complex, heterogeneous, and multicomponent disease in which comorbidities and extra-pulmonary manifestations have important contributions to disease expression, disease burden, and survival".¹² Dyspnea, skeletal muscle dysfunction, decreased exercise capacity, fatigue, cough, sputum, anxiety, depression, pain, sleep disturbances and cognitive decline are profoundly predominant symptoms in patients with COPD.¹³ The patient's capacity to operate regularly in terms of day-to-day activities and physical activity is gradually harmed by these symptoms.¹⁴

1.2 Advancing Non-pharmacological Interventions for COPD care

Pharmacological intervention acts as an essential part of COPD management, however it can not stand alone. Non-pharmacological interventions (NPIs) are other important components that has been shown to be effective and should be used in conjunction with pharmacological therapy.^{15,16} A NPI is defined as any intervention, which is theoretically supported, targeted and replicable, performed on a patient or caregiver and potentially capable of improving health or well-being that does not involve the use of any drugs or medicine.^{17,18} NPIs for people with COPD vary from, ventilator support, and surgical interventions (given to a pre-selected, minority of the patient group) to self-management interventions, multidisciplinary pulmonary rehabilitation including educational

programs, exercise training and behavioural change interventions, which are recommended to the majority of people with COPD, all of which are essential in COPD treatment.^{15,19-22} There is well-documented scientific evidence to prove that NPIs can improve quality of life, slow down deterioration, relieve symptoms, improve self-efficacy for disease management and restore health at a lower economical cost for people with COPD.^{19,23-26} Additionally, the pandemic of The Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)²⁷ has increased interest on NPIs for people with COPD. Study revealed that although the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 in people with COPD is not high, people with COPD hold the highest mortality, which appears to be largely attributable to the presence of comorbidities.²⁸ The pandemic extensive use of medical facilities has limited the therapeutic options available for people with COPD. Remote treatment has emerged as a feasible strategy. NPIs, especially pulmonary rehabilitation has garnered renewed attention since some of them do not necessitate as many medical facilities as pharmacological intervention.

One essential part of NPIs is behaviour change, both for people with COPD and for healthcare professionals. For people with COPD, it is regarding keeping a health promoting behaviour, while for healthcare professionals, it is about keeping a changed way of working. However, there are weak links in the causal chain of current NPI development, which necessitates a thorough and theoretical knowledge of how the interventions fosters change. Since user acceptance from patients toward NPIs are crucial to enable active participation, a better user experience for NPIs is crucial to be offered. Current universal healthcare design relies on traditional expert-driven systems in which patients are not involved in the early stages of the design process.²⁹ One-side information and non-standard theoretical backing limit the comprehension of the mechanism by which change occurs. A complicated influence among the individuals and their surroundings may result in limited success of NPIs.³⁰ In fact, many NPIs are developed and evaluated regarding effect but they are never implemented even though found effective. This is an unfortunate waste of resources. To change this, maximizing and optimizing the engagement of end-users and other stakeholders within the intervention development is required.³⁰

1.3 Co-creation practice in NPI development

Co-creation practice provides a great way to involve people with COPD and other stakeholders in the design of NPIs, and may contribute to increase the patients' adherence to treatment, which in turn yields better clinical outcomes and lower costs.³¹ It has the potential to improve immediate health-related outcomes from individual to systems levels, including

physical health, health-promoting behaviour, self-efficacy for disease management, access to health services, and community relations including social support and networks.³² In addition, the continuous evolving concept of “patient engagement” plays an important role as the healthcare system shifts from disease-centered to patient-centered by defining its four overarching attributes: 1) personalization, 2) access, 3) commitment, and 4) therapeutic alliance (PACT).³³ All of the attributes may necessitate the patient's active participation in the intervention-creation process. However, applying co-creation practice into NPI development is still in its early stages. Some of the research articles reported as co-creation practice but appeared to focus on patient forums, health panels, focus groups and patient interviews, implying that the patient's role is limited to functioning as an information provider rather than an active co-creator.³⁴ It revealed that although co-creation has demonstrated promise, it requires guiding principles and theoretical support to improve its effectiveness.³⁵ With the growing development of NPIs for COPD care, examining the methods used in the co-creation practice in developing NPIs for people with COPD is imperial for improving its further effectiveness. Additionally, identification of a relevant theory or framework prior to practice may result in a more effective intervention than a purely empirical or pragmatic approach.³⁶ Currently, there is no precise or systematic framework for planning or implementing co-creation strategy, as well as assessing their efficacy and impact.³⁷ A systematic co-creation strategy for NPI development may be required to reduce wasteful costs and improve development efficacy for COPD care.

Evidence of a lack of definitional consistency even in the same field is seen in the wide variability of terms used by industry professionals to describe co-creation.³⁸ In the context of using co-creation in developing NPIs in this scoping review, we define co-creation as “co-creation is a branch of participatory research which indicates that ‘end-users’ can be co-creators whose experiences provide value and innovation.”^{39,40} To clarify, co-creation locates on the level six and higher level of the Arnstein's citizen involvement ladder, implying that planning and decision-making responsibilities are at least shared after power redistribution through negotiation between citizens and power holders.⁴¹ There is a containment relationship between ‘end users’ and ‘stakeholders’ in the case of co-creation. ‘End users’ indicate the person who the intervention is designed to target, while stakeholder is defined as a person, group or organization that has interest or concern regarding the end user or the intervention⁴². To enable this scoping review to reveal how differences in participant composition affect the co-creation practice, stakeholders except for end users engagement are not set as a requirement when filtering articles, in spite of repeatedly

mentions of stakeholders in other definitions on co-creation.⁴³ Namely, in the definition of co-creation which will be applied in this scoping review, end-users must be actively involved while the engagement of the stakeholders other than end users is optional.

Current reviews of COPD management interventions are focused on intervention effectiveness⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ rather than examining the development process. In order to aid planning and commissioning of future research, the overall aim of this scoping review is to describe the co-creation practice used when developing NPIs for people with COPD. Specifically, the review will address the core constructs, methods used and challenges faced in the co-creation practice.

2. Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Arksey and O'Malley framework⁴⁹ and recommendations for clarification of the Arksey and O'Malley framework proposed by Levac et al⁵⁰. It will be reported in terms of PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist.⁵¹

2.1 Stage 1: Identify the research question

The literature search, scope and reporting of findings were guided by an overarching question: 'How is co-creation practice used in the development of non-pharmacological health interventions for COPD care?' The question will be addressed in exploring research within the associated set of subtopics to help support the purpose of this review:

- (1) What are the compositions of the co-creator team?
- (2) What kind of NPIs for COPD were targeted?
- (3) What are the methods used for data collection and data analysis when conducting co-creation practice?
- (4) What are the methodologies/theories used?
- (5) What are the challenges, facilitators and barriers faced when using co-creation methods in the development of NPI for COPD care?
- (6) To what extent and in what ways have the co-creation practices been evaluated?

2.2 Stage 2: Identify relevant studies

The purpose of scoping a topic is to be as thorough as possible in identifying primary studies (both published and unpublished) and reviews that are appropriate for answering the research questions.⁴⁹ The following electronic databases will be searched: PubMed, Scopus,

CINAHL, and Web of Science Core Collection (all editions). A key term search strategy will be employed using selected terms. An initial limited search of PubMed was conducted to identify articles on the topic, using the keywords in terms of two groups, “co-creation” and “COPD”. Appendix I contains the full search strategy for PubMed. All of the above-mentioned databases will be searched. We propose to exclude the pharmacological interventions through the title and abstract screening rather than including key terms for “non-pharmacological intervention” in electronic database searches since the search terms for “non-pharmacological intervention” are not easy to comprehensively identify. All articles chosen for inclusion after full-text screening in the scoping review will be used for identifying further references⁴⁹. We propose to review the bibliographies of included articles, and hand-search the “similar studies” and “cited by” sections of included articles to identify additional studies. Relevant gray literature will be manually searched for relevant reports and primary research in ProQuest and NICE Evidence Search for Health and Social Care to reduce publication bias.

2.3 Stage 3: Selecting the studies

Studies will be selected according to a three-step process that will encompass i) managing search results and removing duplicates using Mendeley and Rayyan; ii) title and abstract screening; and iii) full text screening. Title and abstract screening as well as full text screening will be done by at least two reviewers independently.

2.3.1 Inclusion criteria

Studies reporting on the process and analysis applying co-creation practice in developing NPIs for COPD will be included.

Participants

This scoping review will consider studies explicitly describing the co-creation practice in developing NPIs for people with COPD.

Concept

This scoping review is designed to ascertain the challenges faced by co-creation, methods in each co-creation practice for developing NPIs for COPD care, the internal/external facilitators/ obstacles factors when applying co-creation practice in the NPI development practice. Thus, this review will consider studies that explore the use of co-creation practices in the design and development of NPIs for people with COPD. In terms of co-creation, instead of functioning as an information provider, end-users must involve in the

decision making process. According to the Arnstein's citizen involvement ladder⁴¹, we include the studies with the co-creation ideas on the level six (partnership) or higher levels. Studies detailing the development of media that deliver NPIs, such as digital health interventions, will be included as well.

Context

This review will focus on co-creation with the definition “‘end-users’ can be co-creators whose experiences provide value and innovation”. End users include patients, caregivers and healthcare providers. “Value and innovation” implies that ‘end users’ must be actively engaged in the development process of NPIs instead of solely functioning as a provider of information. Studies with end users and other stakeholders engaged can also be included in the scoping review. Eligible studies will not be limited to any geographic location.

2.3.2 Type of resources

This scoping review will consider, but will not be limited to, quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods study designs for inclusion. In addition, reviews addressing the population, concept, and context as previously described will be included. Initially, co-production between service providers and users was investigated in economic study in the 1970s.⁵² Thus, articles published after 1970 and written in English were eligible for inclusion in this review. No limitations will be placed on study design or publication to enhance the comprehensiveness of our results and avoid unintended exclusion of relevant studies.

2.3.3 Exclusion criteria

- (1) Studies examining animal health and study protocol will be excluded.
- (2) To reduce results bias, studies that do not only include people with COPD will be excluded.
- (3) Randomized Controlled Trails (RCT) that do not provide insights regarding a co-creation practice will be excluded.
- (4) Studies focusing on the introduction of the intervention features with co-creation mentioned as part of the strategy but no description will be excluded.
- (5) Studies with end-users acting as information providers but not participating in decision-making will be excluded.

2.4 Stage 4: Charting the data

Data will be extracted and entered into an Excel spreadsheet by at least two independent reviewers. The data extracted will include citation information, and details about the population, concept and context. A draft extraction tool is provided in Appendix II. Since part of the data in included articles will be process-oriented, a qualitative content analysis approach for data analysis is suggested.

2.5 Stage 5: Collating, summarizing, and reporting the results

Stage 5 will be divided into three sub-steps: analysis, reporting, and implication. First, examine the charting data; Second, relate the findings to the study objective and review questions, then report it; Third, consider the implications and significance of the findings for future research, practice and policy.

2.6 Stage 6: Consultation

First, develop an explicit purpose of the consultation based on the purpose of the review and review findings. Second, articulate the type of stakeholders to consult based on the reported data and implications of the review.

3. References

1. 2022 GOLD Reports. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease - GOLD. Published December 7, 2021. Accessed January 21, 2022. <https://goldcopd.org/2022-gold-reports-2/>
2. Halbert RJ, Natoli JL, Gano A, Badamgarav E, Buist AS, Mannino DM. Global burden of COPD: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur Respir J*. 2006;28(3):523-532. doi:10.1183/09031936.06.00124605
3. Perera PN, Armstrong EP, Sherrill DL, Skrepnek GH. Acute exacerbations of COPD in the United States: inpatient burden and predictors of costs and mortality. *COPD*. 2012;9(2):131–141.
4. National Health Service England *Overview of potential to reduce lives lost from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)* 2014. Available from: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/rm-fs-6.pdf>.
5. Who emro. World Health Organization - Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean. Accessed January 21, 2022. <http://www.emro.who.int/health-topics/chronic-obstructive-pulmonary-disease-copd/index.html>

6. Sullivan SD, Ramsey SD, Lee TA. The economic burden of COPD. *Chest*. 2000;117(2):5S-9S. doi:10.1378/chest.117.2_suppl.5s
7. Lu Y, Nyunt MSZ, Gwee X, et al. Life event stress and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): associations with mental well-being and quality of life in a population-based study. *BMJ Open*. 2012;2(6):e001674. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2012-001674
8. Zysman M, Rubenstein J, Le Guillou F, et al. COPD burden on sexual well-being. *Respir Res*. 2020;21(1):311. doi:10.1186/s12931-020-01572-0
9. Vogelmeier CF, Criner GJ, Martinez FJ, et al. Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2017 Report. GOLD Executive Summary. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2017;195: 557-582.
10. Alqahtani JS, Oyelade T, Aldhahir AM, et al. Prevalence, severity and mortality associated with COPD and smoking in patients with COVID-19: A rapid systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(5):e0233147.
11. Miravittles M, Peña-Longobardo LM, Oliva-Moreno J, Hidalgo-Vega Á. Caregivers' burden in patients with COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2015;10:347-356. doi:10.2147/COPD.S76091
12. Vanfleteren LEGW, Spruit MA, Wouters EFM, Franssen FME. Management of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease beyond the lungs. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2016;4(11):911-924.
13. Burtin C, Wadell K. 2021. The rationale for pulmonary rehabilitation. In: Holland AE, Corso SD, Spruit MA. Eds. *Pulmonary Rehabilitation [ERS Monograph]*. Sheffield. European Respiratory Society, 2021; pp. 1-10
14. Miravittles M, Ribera A. Understanding the impact of symptoms on the burden of COPD. *Respir Res*. 2017;18(1). doi:10.1186/s12931-017-0548-3
15. Spruit MA, Singh SJ, Garvey C, et al. An official American Thoracic Society/European Respiratory Society statement: key concepts and advances in pulmonary rehabilitation [published correction appears in *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2014 Jun 15;189(12):1570]. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2013;188(8):e13-e64. doi:10.1164/rccm.201309-1634ST
16. Socialstyrelsen. Nationella riktlinjer för vård vid astma och KOL - Stöd för styrning och ledning. Volume 2022. <https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/globalassets/sharepoint-dokument/artikelkatalog/nationella-riktlinjer/2020-12-7135.pdf>: Socialstyrelsen, 2020.

17. J. Ursa Herguedas A. Non-pharmacological interventions in preventive, rehabilitative and restorative medicine. In: *Alternative Medicine [Working Title]*. IntechOpen; 2020
18. Ninot G. Defining Non-pharmacological Interventions (NPIs). In: *Non-Pharmacological Interventions*. Springer International Publishing; 2021:1-46.
19. Hindelang M, Kirsch F, Leidl R. Effectiveness of non-pharmacological COPD management on health-related quality of life - a systematic review. *Expert Rev Pharmacoecon Outcomes Res.* 2020;20(1):79-91.
doi:10.1080/14737167.2020.1734455
20. Pleguezuelos E, Gimeno-Santos E, Hernández C, et al. Recommendations on non-pharmacological treatment in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease from the Spanish COPD guidelines (GesEPOC 2017). *Arch Bronconeumol.* 2018;54(11):568-575.
doi:10.1016/j.arbr.2018.06.011
21. Sohanpal R, Hooper R, Hames R, Priebe S, Taylor S. Reporting participation rates in studies of non-pharmacological interventions for patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a systematic review. *Syst Rev.* 2012;1(1):66. doi:10.1186/2046-4053-1-66
22. Lutter JI, Lukas M, Schwarzkopf L, et al. Utilization and determinants of use of non-pharmacological interventions in COPD: Results of the COSYCONET cohort. *Respir Med.* 2020;171(106087):106087. doi:10.1016/j.rmed.2020.106087
23. ur Rehman A, Hassali MAA, Abbas S, et al. Pharmacological and non-pharmacological management of COPD; limitations and future prospects: a review of current literature. *Z Gesundh Wiss.* 2020;28(4):357-366. doi:10.1007/s10389-019-01021-3
24. Singh M, Srivastava GN, Yadav D. Effect of non-pharmacological interventions on treatment outcomes in COPD patients: Little changes for bigger rewards. In: *General Practice and Primary Care*. Vol 54. European Respiratory Society; 2019.
25. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease - GOLD. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease - GOLD. Published April 5, 2016. Accessed March 17, 2022. <https://goldcopd.org/>
26. Pauwels RA, Buist AS, Calverley PM, Jenkins CR, Hurd SS, GOLD Scientific Committee. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. NHLBI/WHO Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) Workshop summary: NHLBI/WHO global

- initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) workshop summary. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2001;163(5):1256-1276. doi:10.1164/ajrccm.163.5.2101039
27. Cucinotta D, Vanelli M. WHO declares COVID-19 a pandemic. *Acta Biomed.* 2020;91(1):157-160. doi:10.23750/abm.v91i1.9397
28. Lacedonia D, Scioscia G, Santomasi C, et al. Impact of smoking, COPD and comorbidities on the mortality of COVID-19 patients. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11(1):19251. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-98749-4
29. Andersson T. The medical leadership challenge in healthcare is an identity challenge. *Leadersh Health Serv (Bradf Engl).* 2015;28(2):83-99. doi:10.1108/LHS-04-2014-0032
30. National Health Service England *Overview of potential to reduce lives lost from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)* 2014. Available from: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/rm-fs-6.pdf>.
31. Halvorsrud K, Kucharska J, Adlington K, et al. Identifying evidence of effectiveness in the co-creation of research: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the international healthcare literature. *J Public Health (Oxf).* 2021;43(1):197-208. doi:10.1093/pubmed/fdz126
32. Halvorsrud K, Kucharska J, Adlington K, et al. Identifying evidence of effectiveness in the co-creation of research: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the international healthcare literature. *J Public Health (Oxf).* 2021;43(1):197-208.
33. Higgins T, Larson E, Schnall R. Unraveling the meaning of patient engagement: A concept analysis. *Patient Educ Couns.* 2017;100(1):30-36. doi:10.1016/j.pec.2016.09.002
34. Crawford MJ, Rutter D, Manley C, et al. Systematic review of involving patients in the planning and development of health care. *BMJ.* 2002;325(7375):1263.
35. Matthing J, Sandén B, Edvardsson B. New service development: learning from and with customers. *Int J Serv Ind Manag.* 2004;15(5):479-498.
36. Craig P, Dieppe P, Macintyre S, et al. Developing and evaluating complex interventions: the new Medical Research Council guidance. *BMJ.* 2008;337:a1655. doi:10.1136/bmj.a1655
37. Greenhalgh T, Jackson C, Shaw S, Janamian T. Achieving research impact through co-creation in community-based health services: literature review and case study. *Milbank Q.* 2016;94:392–429.

38. Pearce T, Maple M, Shakeshaft A, Wayland S, McKay K. What is the Co-Creation of New Knowledge? A Content Analysis and Proposed Definition for Health Interventions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020; 17(7):2229. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072229>
39. Prahalad CK, Ramaswamy V. Co-Opting Customer Competence. *Harvard Business Review*. 2000;78:79–90.
40. von Hippel E. *Democratizing Innovation*. MIT Press; 2006.
41. Arnstein's ladder of citizen participation. Citizenshandbook.org. Accessed May 18, 2022. <https://www.citizenshandbook.org/arnsteinsladder.html>
42. Post JE, Preston LE, Sachs S. *Redefining the Corporation: Stakeholder Management and Organizational Wealth*. Stanford University Press; 2002.
43. Zwass V. Co-creation: Toward a taxonomy and an integrated research perspective. *Int J Electron Commer*. 2010;15(1):11-48.
44. Shaw G, Whelan ME, Armitage LC, Roberts N, Farmer AJ. Are COPD self-management mobile applications effective? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *NPJ Prim Care Respir Med*. 2020;30(1):11. doi:10.1038/s41533-020-0167-1
45. Li LSK, Butler S, Goldstein R, Brooks D. Comparing the impact of different exercise interventions on fatigue in individuals with COPD: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Chron Respir Dis*. 2019;16:1479973119894855. doi:10.1177/1479973119894855
46. Simonelli C, Vitacca M, Vignoni M, Ambrosino N, Paneroni M. Effectiveness of manual therapy in COPD: A systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Pulmonology*. 2019;25(4):236-247. doi:10.1016/j.pulmoe.2018.12.008
47. Jang S, Kim Y, Cho WK. A systematic review and meta-analysis of telemonitoring interventions on severe COPD exacerbations. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(13):6757. doi:10.3390/ijerph18136757
48. Armstrong M, Winnard A, Chynkiamis N, Boyle S, Burtin C, Vogiatzis I. Use of pedometers as a tool to promote daily physical activity levels in patients with COPD: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur Respir Rev*. 2019;28(154):190039. doi:10.1183/16000617.0039-2019
49. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *Int J Soc Res Methodol*. 2005;8(1):19-32.
50. Levac D, Colquhoun H, O'Brien KK. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implement Sci*. 2010;5(1):69.

51. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169(7):467-473.
52. Grönroos C. Conceptualising value co-creation: A journey to the 1970s and back to the future. *J Mark Manag.* 2012;28(13-14):1520-1534.
doi:10.1080/0267257x.2012.737357

Appendix

Appendix I: Search strategy

Database: PubMed

Date	Query	Records retrieved
Search conducted in 29 th Jan 2022	("COPD"[Title/Abstract] OR "chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*"[Title/Abstract] OR "chronic obstructive lung disease*"[Title/Abstract] OR "chronic obstructive airway disease*"[Title/Abstract] OR "pulmonary disease, chronic obstructive"[MeSH Terms] OR "Asthma-Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Overlap Syndrome"[MeSH Terms] OR "Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Obstructive, Severe Early-Onset"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("participatory"[Title/Abstract] OR "stakeholder engagement"[Title/Abstract] OR "shared decision making"[Title/Abstract] OR "user involvement"[Title/Abstract] OR "experience based co design"[Title/Abstract] OR "Co-creat*"[Title/Abstract] OR "co-design*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Co-conception"[Title/Abstract] OR "Co-production"[Title/Abstract] OR "Public and patient involvement"[Title/Abstract] OR "Public participation"[Title/Abstract] OR "Collaborative design"[Title/Abstract] OR "stakeholder participation"[MeSH Terms] OR "community based participatory research"[MeSH Terms] OR "Citizen Science"[MeSH Terms])	152 results (after limiting to English and after 1970)

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument

Extraction Elements:

Variable	
Title	
Author(s), Year, Location	
NPI	
Stages of COPD patients	
Timing of intervention	
Study aim	
Study design	
Co-creators	

Theory/methodology mentioned when using co-creation	
Number of co-creation sessions	
Data collection methods	
Data analysis methods	
Factors facilitating the applied co-creation methods	
Factors inhibiting the applied co-creation methods	
Is co-creation process evaluated?	
Is the ownership of co-creators discussed?	
Essential factors of NPI for COPD	
Notes	